

**Machine Learning-based Provenance Analysis of Portuguese Chalcolithic
Variscite: New Insights from n=170 Green Phosphate Beads.**

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ABSTRACT

This study applies VORTEX (Variscite ORigin TEchnology X-ray based), a recently published machine learning framework (Sánchez-Gómez et al., 2026), to determine the geological provenance of n=170 prehistoric green phosphate artifacts from four Portuguese archaeological sites: Tholos do Barro (TdB), Leceia (L), Necrópole de Alcalar (NdA) and Penha Verde (PV). VORTEX integrates portable X-ray fluorescence (p-XRF) compositional data, Random Forest classification, and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) techniques to provide probabilistic provenance determinations with quantified uncertainty.

Our results confirm Aliste (Zamora) as the principal supplier of variscite to Portuguese sites, with 90.4% of confidently classified beads attributed to this source (average confidence: 93.6% ± 7.2). A limited but significant contribution from Gavà (9.6%, n=13) was detected, while no evidence supporting Encinasola as a source was found. These findings corroborate recent revisions to earlier archaeological assumptions and reinforce emerging perspectives on Iberian variscite exchange networks. Notably, the high-confidence Gavà attributions — concentrated at NdA and PV — present interpretative challenges regarding chronological and cultural

connections between Portuguese Chalcolithic sites and Catalan Neolithic mining contexts.

This work presents the first provenance analysis of TdB and NdA assemblages and makes publicly available previously unpublished compositional data for all studied sites, demonstrating the scalability and applicability of the VORTEX framework to real-world archaeological datasets while contributing new empirical evidence for understanding prehistoric exchange networks in Western Iberia.

Keywords: Variscite, Provenance analysis, Portuguese Prehistory, Machine Learning, Explainable AI (XAI), p-XRF, prehistoric exchange networks, Iberian Peninsula, VORTEX

Introduction

In late prehistoric Europe, variscite ($\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and other related green phosphate minerals carved into personal ornaments (beads, pendants, and amulets) stand out as exceptional markers of exchange networks. Their archaeological significance stems from their limited geological availability, evidence of long-distance trade, potentially distinctive geochemical signature, and profound cultural significance derived from their exotic nature and association with prestigious consumption, as expressed by their appearance in megalithic burials linked to the collective identities of high-status individuals. (Alarashi and Borrell, 2020; Kuhn and Stiner, 2007; Odriozola et al., 2016, 2010; Schulz Paulsson, 2017; Schulz Paulsson et al., 2019; Stiner, 2014; Thomas, 2011).

The term "callaite," coined by Pliny the Elder, has described prehistoric green stone adornments since Roman times and persists as a generic category encompassing diverse raw materials, creating considerable confusion. While often equated with variscite, numerous studies (Canelhas, 1973; Guitán Rivera and Vázquez-Varela, 1983; Odriozola et al., 2016; Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2024; Vázquez Varela, 1975) demonstrate that not all green stones are variscite and not all variscite is green, underscoring the need for reliable raw material characterization when modeling prehistoric exchange networks. This distinction proves crucial in provenance

analysis: green phosphates originate from well-characterized geological sources amenable to sourcing studies, whereas diverse greenstone materials—presumed locally sourced—remain insufficiently characterized for reliable provenance determination. Consequently, uncertainty regarding raw material composition represents a critical methodological challenge, as grouping disparate materials obscures meaningful patterns in acquisition, production, and circulation essential for reconstructing prehistoric social and economic interactions.

Concerning green phosphates, early 19th-century hypotheses proposed diverse origins, including eastern Mediterranean sources (Ferreira, 1953). Following discovery of major Iberian exploitation areas from the mid-20th century onwards, researchers increasingly favored peninsular origins. Currently, approximately a dozen variscite outcrops are documented across Western Europe (Cassen et al., 2019; Fábregas Valcarce and Rodríguez-Rellán, 2019; Marini et al., 1989; Meireles et al., 1987; Odriozola et al., 2010; Querré et al., 2008), though prehistoric exploitation evidence remains absent at most locations. Thus, the prevailing consensus identifies three primary Iberian centers—Aliste (Zamora), Encinasola (Huelva), and Gavá (Catalonia)—as principal sources supplying extensive distribution networks that circulated variscite ornaments throughout Western Europe during late prehistory (Blanco Majado et al., 1995; Blasco et al., 1990; Dominguez-Bella, 2004; Odriozola et al., 2016; Querré et al., 2019b; Villalobos García and Odriozola, 2016).

The prehistoric Variscite exchange in Portugal

In Portugal, 'Calaites' have been documented in Neolithic and Chalcolithic contexts, both funerary and domestic, since the mid-19th century, although it was not until the second half of the 20th century that research included a systematic mineral characterisation programme that made it possible to assess the relative distribution of the raw materials and to integrate them into a regional research agenda interested in their distribution patterns, formal typologies, use and symbolism (Carvalho, 2019).

In the 19th century, pioneering work by A. Bensaúde (Bensaúde, 1884) and É. Cartailhac (Cartailhac, 1886) initiated systematic investigation of 'Calaite' artifacts, establishing foundational research questions concerning geographical distribution, possible origins—recognizing variability suggesting multiple sources—and identifying major consumption centers such as the Tagus estuary. The Leisners' investigations proved crucial in establishing the artifacts' chronology and association with Iberian megalithism, definitively refuting Eastern origin hypotheses through radiocarbon dating of nine beads from Carapito I dolmen (Beira Alta) at approximately 3700-3500 cal BC (GrN-5110: 4850 ± 40 BP), predating coastal Portuguese finds and dismantling the 'Orientalist' paradigm dominating early 20th-century scholarship (Carvalho, 2019; Leisner and Leisner, 1951; Leisner and Ribeiro, 1968). Subsequently, advancing analytical methods enabled comprehensive mineralogical characterization of multiple site assemblages (Canelhas, 1973; Carvalho, 2019, 2005; Jorge, 1981), revealing widespread greenstone—particularly variscite—distribution throughout Portuguese territory with significant concentrations around the Tagus.

The oldest variscite ornaments recorded in Portugal are limited to megalithic monuments in Beira Alta and Trás-os-Montes provinces, attributed to the 4th millennium BCE through radiocarbon dating at sites including Outeiro de Gregos 2 (Baião), Areita (São João da Pesqueira), and Sangrino (Penedono) (Canelhas, 1973; Carvalho, 2005; Jorge, 1981), suggesting the Douro valley as the entry point and distribution route for Aliste variscite. In Portuguese Estremadura, and southern Portugal, distribution models remain inadequate, as the nearest source in Encinasola appears conspicuously underrepresented archaeologically, though notable exceptions such as Povoado dos Perdigões suggest preliminary connections. Variscite circulation peaked between 3500 and 2300 BC, consistent with broader peninsular trends, with subsequent decline potentially delayed along the Atlantic façade (Carvalho, 2019; Rodríguez-Rellán and Valcarce, 2018; Schulz Paulsson et al., 2019).

Despite significant advances made in the early 21st century, challenges remain; the lack of compositional analyses makes it difficult to accurately differentiate between variscite and other green stones and complicates the assignment of provenance

(Odriozola, 2015; Viel et al., 2015), while debates continue about the reliability of provenance models based on geochemical markers due to divergent analytical protocols and evolving instrumental standards (C. P. Odriozola et al., 2013; Odriozola, 2015; Querré et al., 2014a). Although spatial and exploratory network analyses (Rellan et al., 2023) have enhanced understanding of artifact circulation, the precise structure, mechanisms, and temporal dynamics of exchange networks remain incompletely resolved.

The VORTEX Framework for Variscite Provenance

VORTEX (Variscite ORigin TEchnology X-ray based) is a machine learning-based framework integrating portable X-ray fluorescence (p-XRF) compositional analysis, Random Forest classification, and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) techniques, developed to address persistent limitations in variscite provenance analysis including insufficient geological sampling, the absence of probabilistic interpretive frameworks, and limited analytical scalability (Sánchez-Gomez et al., 2026). The framework was trained on the largest geoarchaeological green phosphate compositional dataset assembled to date (n=1,778 geological samples from Aliste, Gavá, and Encinasola) (Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2025) and externally validated with 95% classification accuracy. It provides probabilistic provenance predictions with adjustable confidence thresholds, and employs two complementary XAI techniques — Recursive Feature Elimination with Cross-Validation (RFECV) (Guyon et al., 2002) and Shapley values (Shapley, 1953) — to identify which compositional features contribute most to classification decisions.

Geochemical significance of XAI-derived feature importance

Provenance research on variscite has followed the provenance postulate (Weigand et al., 1977), seeking elemental features with greater inter-source than intra-source variability to serve as diagnostic markers for individual deposits. These efforts have relied on compositional data obtained through analytical methods such as PIXE, FTIR spectroscopy, SEM-EDX, MAS-NMR, XRD, and ICP-MS-LA (Blanco Majado et

al., 1995; Dominguez-Bella, 2004; Domínguez-Bella et al., 2019; Dominguez-Bella et al., 2002; Edo Benaiges et al., 1998; Herbaut and Querré, 2004; Odriozola et al., 2016, 2010; Querré, 2007; Querré et al., 2014b, 2014b, 2008), which, although analytically powerful, impose significant practical constraints: they require transporting materials to specialised facilities, demand highly trained personnel for data interpretation, pose risks to the integrity of heritage-sensitive artefacts, and incur substantial costs associated with equipment access, insurance, and sample transport. These limitations have directly constrained the empirical basis available for provenance modelling, as the number of geological reference samples that can be analysed remains small relative to the compositional variability within and between deposits. VORTEX addresses this scalability problem by combining portable X-ray fluorescence — which enables non-destructive, in situ analysis at a fraction of the cost and logistical overhead — with machine learning and XAI techniques capable of investigating discriminatory proxies from the larger datasets that p-XRF makes feasible.

The provenance models built upon these earlier analytical foundations have progressively expanded their elemental inventories: initial studies proposed Fe, Cr, Ca, and Si based on 8 samples (Blanco Majado et al., 1995; Edo Benaiges et al., 1998), subsequent work added V using 16 samples (Dominguez-Bella, 2004; Dominguez-Bella et al., 2002; Herbaut and Querré, 2004), then P/Al atomic ratios with ternary diagrams based on 36 p-XRF analyses (Odriozola, 2015; Villalobos García and Odriozola, 2016), and most recently a rule-based model incorporating eight elements through multiple binary and ternary correlations based on approximately 200 analyses (Querré et al., 2019a). These models, though increasingly comprehensive, share two fundamental limitations: the oversimplification of the discriminatory space — reducing complex multi-elemental compositions to binary or ternary relationships between a small number of preselected elements — and the restricted empirical basis upon which they were constructed, ranging from 8 to approximately 200 samples. These constraints compound one another: with limited data, simpler discriminant schemes may appear adequate, but when exposed to larger datasets that better capture intra-source compositional variability, their discriminatory criteria tend to overlap and fail (Barroso et al., 2021, p. 187).

VORTEX takes a fundamentally different approach, rather than constraining discrimination to a predetermined set of elemental ratios or ternary projections, it operates across an expanded compositional space leveraging XAI techniques to quantify each element's relative contribution to the classification task offering an intuitive representation of high-dimensional compositional patterns that models limited to ternary relationships cannot capture (for further information on the geochemical significance of the characteristics derived from XAI, please refer to the Supplementary material).

Objectives of this Study

This study applies the VORTEX framework to n=170 green phosphate beads from four Portuguese archaeological sites: Tholos do Barro (TdB), Leceia (L), Necrópole de Alcalar (NdA), and Penha Verde (PV). While materials from L, and PV have undergone previous provenance analyses using different methodological approaches (C. Odriozola et al., 2013b, 2013b; Querré et al., 2014b), the compositional data remain unpublished until now. TdB and NdA represent the first provenance analysis of these assemblages.

Our objectives are threefold: (1) to demonstrate VORTEX's applicability to real-world archaeological datasets and validate its performance against previously studied assemblages, (2) to expand understanding of variscite distribution patterns in Portugal through new data from TdB and NdA and (3) to make publicly available previously unpublished compositional data, enabling independent verification and future comparative research.

Figure 1 - **General map.** Location of sites and green phosphate sources studied here: Necrópole de Alcalar (NdA, n= 65); Leceia (L, n= 37); Tholos do Barro (TdB, n= 32); Penha Verde (PV, n= 36).

Materials and Methods

The VORTEX Framework: a quick overview

The framework employs a Random Forest classifier trained on n=1,778 geoarchaeological samples from the three main Iberic deposits: Aliste n=511, Gavà n=828, Encinasola n=439)(Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2025). Compositional data were acquired using an Oxford Instrument XMET-7500 handheld XRF equipped with a Rhodium tube, a silicon drift detector, and an automatic 5-position filter changer, with quantification via the fundamental parameter method (SOILS-LE programme). This method is particularly effective for analyzing a large number of elements, making it well suited for this study (Beckhoff et al., 2006). Elements from Al to Th were measured in 60-second analyses; calibration was monitored using a BCR-032 natural Moroccan phosphate standard¹ and samples were analysed directly without

¹ Standard measurements are reported in the dataset.

preparation. All concentrations were converted to atomic percentages, below detection limit values were imputed as $LoD/\sqrt{2}$ (Croghan, 2003)², and compositions were closed at 100%. Originally, the model was trained on a set of 37 features, to which an analysis of variable importance was subsequently applied using RFECV and Shapley value analysis, enabling the identification of the most informative features for distinguishing between each of the deposits (Figure 3). For detailed methodological information, including mathematical formulation, hyperparameter optimisation, training protocols, and validation procedures, see (Sánchez-Gomez et al., 2026); for data acquisition protocols and the complete training dataset, see (Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2025).

For the practical application of this study, the original workflow was slightly modified by removing features whose recorded values were present in fewer than 10% of cases³, resulting in a final set of 18 informative features used as predictors, with which the model was retrained (see Analytical boundaries section for further details).

² LoD specified for each matrix at 3σ (99.7% confidence), with LoDs improving as a function of \sqrt{t} .

³ TI has been removed because it accounts for only 10.2% of the values recorded in the training set.

Figure 3 - Feature Importance Analysis. (A) RFECV showing model performance as a function of the number of selected features. Cross-validation accuracy plateaus at approximately 14 features, defining the VORTEX Distilled model. (B–D) SHAP plots illustrating local feature contributions for each geological source: Aliste (B), Gavá (C), and Encinasola (D). Each point represents one geological training sample; horizontal position indicates the SHAP value (impact on classification probability), and colour encodes the feature value (yellow = high, purple = low). For Aliste, low values of As and Mo produce positive SHAP contributions, while high Ca generates strong negative contributions. For Gavá, high Ca, Sr, and Ba are the principal positive drivers. For Encinasola, Ca, V, As, and K show the strongest influence.

Uncertainty Assessment and Provenance Determination

The classification process outputs probabilistic predictions — a vector of membership probabilities for each source — rather than deterministic assignments.

An adjustable confidence threshold (τ) filters low-confidence predictions as "uncertain," while a consistency metric C quantifies whether samples from a given site converge on a single source or reflect multiple provenances. C is given by:

$$C(Y) = \frac{|x_i \in Y : x_i = \text{mode}(Y)|}{|Y|}$$

Where: Y is the set of confident predictions for a site (predictions with confidence $\geq \tau$), x_i are the individual predictions, $\text{mode}(Y)$ is the most frequent source in Y , and $|Y|$ is the number of samples used for provenance analysis.

Additionally, median entropy per site quantifies prediction uncertainty — interpretable as intra-site compositional variability — while the percentage of uncertain classifications at each threshold is reported explicitly, enabling transparent adjustment of source–site links and systematic exploration of how parameter choices affect network-level inferences.

Sensitivity analysis for different confidence thresholds

To evaluate the robustness of provenance determinations against threshold selection, we performed a sensitivity analysis across five confidence values ($\tau = 0.60, 0.65, 0.70, 0.75, \text{ and } 0.80$). For each threshold, we recalculated the proportion of samples classified as uncertain (confidence $< \tau$), the consensus source per site, the homogeneity index C , and the median prediction entropy. This analysis allows us to assess whether archaeological interpretations —site-source links— remain stable across a range of τ values or are contingent upon a specific threshold choice. The baseline threshold ($\tau = 0.70$) was adopted as a balanced compromise between data retention and prediction confidence.

Archaeological data

We analysed $n=170$ variscite artefacts from four Neolithic to Chalcolithic Portuguese archaeological sites (Table 1; see supplementary material for detailed descriptions of

the contexts). The selection of sites covers a range of geographical locations, functional types, and chronological spans, enabling a robust assessment of VORTEX's applicability across different archaeological contexts. In particular:

Penha Verde (PV, n=36): is a fortified settlement in the Serra de Sintra, dated to the second half of the 3rd–early 2nd millennium BCE (Cardoso, 2010). Previous provenance analyses attribute its variscite to Aliste (C. Odriozola et al., 2013b; Querré et al., 2014b).

Tholos do Barro (TdB, n=32): is a collective burial at Monte da Pena (Torres Vedras), with a rich Chalcolithic funerary assemblage (Madeira et al., 1972). First provenance analysis of this assemblage.

Leceia (L, n=36): is a fortified settlement in Oeiras spanning the late Neolithic to late Chalcolithic (Cardoso, 2022, 2011). Previously attributed to Aliste (C. Odriozola et al., 2013b; Querré et al., 2014b).

Necrópole de Alcalar (NdA, n=66): the largest tholos necropolis in Portugal (Portimão, Algarve), part of a major 3rd-millennium BCE complex (Morán, 2019; Sousa et al., 2024). First provenance analysis of this assemblage; its proximity to Encinasola provides a critical test for evaluating that source's role in distribution networks

Table 1 - **Summary description of archaeological sites studied here.**

Site	Samples Analyzed	Type/Function	Period	Previous Provenance Attribution
Tholos do Barro (TdB)	32	<i>Tholos</i> /Funerary	Chalcolithic	No
Leceia (L)	36	Walled Enclosure/settlement	Neo?-Chalcolithic	Aliste ⁴
Necrópole de Alcalar	66	Tholos, Necrópole	Chalcolithic	No

⁴(C. Odriozola et al., 2013b; Querré et al., 2014b)

Penha Verde (PV)	36	Walled Enclosure/settlement	Chalcolithic	Aliste ⁵
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Methodological caveats and Analytical boundaries

XAI techniques explain model behaviour, not geochemistry. A high SHAP or feature importance score for a feature indicates that the model relies heavily on it for classification, which supports — though does not prove — its geochemical relevance. Consequently, the information obtained using these techniques must always be cross-checked against independent expert knowledge and mineralogical information.

The analysis is further constrained by the compositional nature of the feature space. Elemental concentrations measured by pXRF are inherently compositional: they carry only relative meaning and are subject to a constant-sum constraint (Aitchison, 1986; Greenacre and Wood, 2024; Martín-Fernández et al., 2003; Pawlowsky-Glahn and Egozcue, 2006). A fundamental consequence of this structure is that the values assigned to any given element depend on which other elements are included in the dataset, adding or removing components and renormalising to 1 – or 100% – will alter all values, summary statistics, and analytical results. This dependency is compounded by the limitations of pXRF itself, which might not reliably detect certain elements, meaning that the observed dataset always constitutes a subcomposition of a potentially larger composition. Closure can therefore induce spurious correlations that distort the results of statistical analyses, potentially misrepresenting variable-importance rankings and decision boundaries when standard multivariate methods are applied to compositional data without appropriate transformation.

Random Forest is less sensitive to this constraint than distance- or covariance-based methods, because its predictions emerge from ensembles of independently bootstrapped decision trees, each trained on a random subset of predictors, rather than from covariance structure directly (Hastie et al., 2009; Sanchez-Gomez et al., 2024, p. 8). The model is consequently best interpreted as a predictive classifier rather than a strictly inferential geochemical model. For this reason, the results would

⁵ (C. Odriozola et al., 2013a)

benefit from being cross-checked against independent mineralogical analyses such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), and comparing the results across different compositional representations remains a necessary step in refining the proposed workflow.

Results

Provenance analysis revealed a predominant supply from Aliste, with limited contribution from Gavá and no evidence of Encinasola sourcing. Across all sites, 122 beads (90.4%) were attributed to Aliste with high average prediction confidence ($93.6\% \pm 7.2$), while 13 beads (9.6%) were attributed to Gavá at somewhat lower average confidence ($84.2\% \pm 10.0$) (figure 4, table 2). Examination of site-specific patterns revealed some variation in both source diversity and attribution confidence. TdB exhibited complete homogeneity (100% Aliste, $95.5\% \pm 5.9$ average confidence) with the lowest median entropy (0.18) and minimal uncertainty (3.1%, $n=1$), indicating a strong and unambiguous connection with Aliste as the sole source. L displayed predominantly Aliste attribution (92.6%, $92.1\% \pm 7.5$ average confidence) alongside a minor Gavá component ($n=2$, 7.4%); it exhibited a relatively elevated uncertainty rate (25.0%, $n=9$) and a moderate median entropy (0.57), suggesting greater intra-assemblage variability. Its two Gavá-attributed beads, however, were assigned with comparatively low confidence (73.7% and 71.3%), the weakest Gavá signal among all sites. PV showed strong Aliste dominance (94.1%, $95.3\% \pm 5.9$ average confidence) with low median entropy (0.21) and minimal uncertainty (5.6%, $n=2$), alongside a minor Gavá contribution ($n=2$, 5.9%). Critically, its two Gavá-attributed beads demonstrated high confidence scores ($95.1\% \pm 2.0$; 96.5% and 93.6%), suggesting a strong connection signal between PV and the Catalan source that should be further investigated (see discussion). NdA, the largest assemblage in the study, also showed Aliste as the leading source (79.1%, $91.2\% \pm 8.4$ average confidence) but displayed the most pronounced Gavá presence of the dataset (20.9%, $n=9$, $84.4\% \pm 9.2$ average confidence). This site showed the highest median entropy (0.79), the highest uncertainty rate (35.8%, $n=24$), and the lowest homogeneity (0.79). Several of its Gavá-attributed beads were nonetheless assigned with high confidence (up to 94.5%), pointing to a non-negligible Catalan contribution at this site (see discussion). All sites achieved consensus classification as Aliste,

reinforcing its central role as the primary provenance source for the studied assemblages.

Figure 4- **Probability distribution of model predictions for each site.** Each point represents an individual prediction coloured with the label assigned by the model.

The red line represents the established confidence threshold. Only predictions with a confidence level ≥ 0.70 have been used to determine provenance.

Table 2 - **Summary table for provenance analysis with VORTEX.** Gavá (G), Encinasola (E), Aliste (A).

Site	Samples analyzed	G	E	A	Uncertain(%)	Samples for provenance	Median entropy	Consensus	Homogeneity
TdB	32	1	0	31	3.12	31	0.18	Aliste	1.0
L	36	5	0	31	25	27	0.57	Aliste	0.93
NdA	66	16	0	51	35.82	43	0.79	Aliste	0.79
PV	36	2	0	34	5.56	34	0.21	Aliste	0.94

Sensitivity Analysis:

As expected, the proportion of samples classified as uncertain increased with the threshold, rising from 7.6% ($n=13$) at $\tau = 0.60$ to 31.0% ($n=53$) at $\tau = 0.80$ (Figure 5). This increase was not uniformly distributed across sites. NdA exhibited the greatest sensitivity to threshold variation, with uncertainty rates rising from 13.4% to 49.3%, followed by L (8.3% to 38.9%). PV displayed moderate sensitivity (2.8% to 11.1%), whereas TdB remained the least affected across the entire range (0.0% to 6.3%).

It is important to note that the consensus source attribution remained consistent across all four sites at every threshold analysed, with Aliste consistently identified as the dominant source and no consensus changes relative to the baseline ($\tau = 0.70$). Site-level homogeneity increased with the threshold, as progressively excluding low-confidence beads left a more uniform set of confident attributions: mean homogeneity rose from 0.887 at $\tau = 0.60$ to 0.948 at $\tau = 0.80$. This trend was most pronounced at the more heterogeneous sites — NdA ranged from 0.759 to 0.853 and L from 0.879 to 1.000 — whereas PV remained essentially stable (0.938–0.943) and TdB stayed at or near perfect homogeneity (0.969–1.000). Across the entire range, the dominant-source consensus proved robust to the choice of threshold.

Figure 5 . **Sensitivity analysis of provenance determinations across confidence thresholds** . **A**: Solid lines (left axis) show the percentage of samples classified as uncertain per site; dashed lines (right axis) show homogeneity values. **B**: Heatmap of homogeneity values per site and threshold, with consensus source indicated on the right; the red rectangle highlights the baseline threshold. All sites maintain Aliste (PDLC) as the consensus source across all thresholds.

Discussion

The model's results are consistent with the archaeological evidence relating to the phenomenon of greenstone ornaments in the south-west of the Iberian Peninsula and reinforce Aliste's predominant role as the main supplier of these materials during its Chalcolithic heyday. As for the compositional analysis of the confident Gavà-attributed beads ($n = 11$; seven at NdA, two at PV, two at L) this reveals a set of geochemically based but interpretatively heterogeneous signals, rather than a single, coherent Catalan signature. The clearest geochemical support comes from one NdA specimen (MNA161-ALC3_10045), whose Ca concentration (12.05%) is the highest in the entire assemblage (98.8th percentile of all 171 cases). This is consistent with the calcium-rich phosphate assemblages —crandallite, monetite, planerite— documented exclusively in the Gavà mines and attributed to the geochemical influence of the Garraf dolomites (Borrell and Bosch, 2013; Edo Benaiges et al., 1992). Ca remains among the most influential features for Gavà classification in the SHAP analysis (mean $|\text{SHAP}| = 0.200$), and for this bead its discriminatory role is geochemically interpretable rather than a statistical artefact.

The remaining NdA attributions, however, are more equivocal. Their Ca contents are only moderate (2.5–4.5%) and, they carry relatively elevated Cr (up to 1.73%, mean 1.02%) together with detectable As (up to 0.095%) and V (0.15–0.31%) — a trace-element profile that runs counter to the leaching-depleted signature expected for the Gavà host schists. Only the two PV specimens display the clean low-V/Cr/As pattern (Cr 0.11–0.15%, As 0.003–0.005%, V below detection) that the geochemical model associates with Gavà and that simultaneously argues against Encinasola, where As and V are influential discriminators. This internal split indicates that, beyond the single high-Ca NdA bead and the two low-trace PV beads, several NdA attributions are better understood as borderline model decisions near the Gavà/Aliste boundary than as positive geochemical matches, a behaviour expected near the limits of the model's decision boundaries, where small compositional differences are enough to tip a sample from one source to another.

These attributions, regardless of their geochemical signature, raise substantial chronological and geographical concerns. The documented exploitation of Can Tintorer ceased by approximately 3450 cal BC (Borrell, 2025; Morell-Rovira et al.,

2023; Schulz Paulsson et al., 2019), while both NdA and PV are mainly Chalcolithic contexts dating to the 3rd millennium BC (Cardoso, 2010; Morán, 2019; C. Odriozola et al., 2013b; Sousa et al., 2024), implying a gap of 500–1000 years between the end of Catalan mining operations and the depositional contexts of these beads.

Moreover, the consolidated distribution model for Gavà describes a classical distance-decay pattern concentrated in north-eastern Iberia and the Ebro valley (Rellán et al., 2023); against this background, Alcalar (Algarve), over 800 km from the Catalan mines, lies well beyond the network's documented range, a distance whose only emerging parallels in the south-west remain to be independently confirmed. In contrast, Aliste, which accounts for 79.1% of confident NdA attributions and dominated western Iberian supply during the 3rd millennium through directional trade networks reaching the Tagus estuary and beyond, represents a far more parsimonious supplier for the Algarve. The geochemical heterogeneity of the assemblage attributed to Gavà, combined with this problematic chronological and spatial association, reinforces the interpretation that Aliste is the dominant source, a conclusion to which the model points through its consensus-based decision-making process.

The PV specimens compound these interpretative challenges in a different way. Their anomalous P/Al ratios (0.222 and 0.309), far below variscite stoichiometry, combined with Si concentrations of 37–41%, indicate a silicate-phosphate mineral assemblage rather than variscite *sensu stricto*, consistent with the distinct phosphate minerals documented across Iberian deposits and the broad compositional variability inherent to phosphate chemistry. Their moderate Ca (2.7–4.3%) provides a weak affinity with the Gavà Ca-enrichment pattern, and their high confidence in the attribution appears to emerge from the cumulative exclusion of Aliste and Encinasola through multiple moderate feature contributions rather than a dominant Ca-driven signal. The two L specimens, attributed at lower confidence (0.71–0.74) and showing neither the high-Ca nor the silicate-phosphate signatures (Ca 2.1–4.9%, P/Al 0.9–1.0), similarly sit at the margins of the Gavà compositional domain. Together, these cases underscore the limitations of a three-source classification framework when confronted with mineralogically heterogeneous archaeological assemblages that may fall outside the compositional domains represented in the training data.

Three non-exclusive explanations remain viable: (a) these beads represent genuine Gavá imports with extended biographical trajectories spanning the chronological gap, which, while unprecedented, cannot be excluded given the limited knowledge of artifact biographies in Iberian megalithic contexts; (b) the beads were deposited during an earlier phase in the prolonged use-life of these monuments. Iberian megalithic monuments and necropolises were characteristically subject to discontinuous reuse, often spanning the fourth and third millennia BC, and the antiquity of most excavations at Alcalar makes it difficult to assign individual ornaments to discrete depositional events (Sousa et al., 2024). Under this scenario, a Gavá ornament, a material whose extraction at Can Tintorer is a Neolithic phenomenon, could have entered the monument during an earlier, late-Neolithic episode and become incorporated into an assemblage otherwise dominated by third-millennium material. That such early variscite circulation, although exceptional, reached the south-west is independently attested at Neolithic contexts such as the Alberite dolmen, for which a comparable Gavá attribution has recently been reported (Sánchez-Gomez et al., 2026, p. 8). Were further cases of this kind confirmed, the implication would be a substantial reassessment of the chronological depth and spatial reach of the Gavá distribution network, extending it beyond what is currently documented for north-eastern Iberia and the Ebro valley; (c) The model identifies Ca-enriched compositions or those with complementary geochemical signatures, within a three-class framework, identifying Gavá as the source whose training set provides the best fit, although the actual origin could be an unsampled section of the extensive Aliste geological formation or another source that has not yet been characterised. Mineralogical confirmation via X-ray diffraction (XRD), selective geochemical sampling of poorly explored green phosphate deposits, and further statistical modelling of intra-deposit variability would help to distinguish between these hypotheses.

Appendices

- Dataset appendix 1

- Supplementary material appendix 2
- Reproducible workflow appendix 3

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Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

- Data are available online: <https://zenodo.org/records/21042465>
- Scripts and code are available online:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17242039>;
- Supplementary information and specific reproducibility material is available online: <https://zenodo.org/records/21042465>

Conflict of interest disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

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